

Biosynthetic studies on biologically active alkaloids from Indian medicinal plants[†]

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Recognising the importance of alkaloids and alkaloid biosynthesis and having an interest in biologically active natural products, a study was initiated to investigate the alkaloids of Indian medicinal plants which show consistent biological activity when screened or have a reputation in folk lore medicine. The expectations of this programme were not that it would provide a large number of new drug molecules but would give new leads. The work carried out by us in this area is as follows :

Alkaloids of *Croton sparsiflorus* Morong¹

A search for hypotensive agents in the alkaloidal fraction of the ethanolic extract of *C. sparsiflorus* Morong in which the hypotensive activity was concentrated, led to the isolation of several proaporphine, dihydroproaporphine and aporphine alkaloids¹. Of the isolated alkaloids, *N*-methylcrotsparine (1) is a potent hypotensive agent, *N*-methylcrotsparinine (2) produces an initial sharp transient fall of blood pressure followed by a gradual sustained hypotension at 3 to 5 mg/kg dose. *N*-Methylsparsiflorine (3) methiodide also produces hypotension of the same magnitude. The structure and stereochemistry of crotsparine (1), crotsparinine (2) and *N*-methylcrotsparine (3) have been determined¹. The absolute configuration of crotsparine, crotsparinine and sparsiflorine has been determined². The biosynthesis of crotsparine, crotsparinine and sparsiflorine has been studied³. The evidence supports the direct oxidative coupling of (+)-, and (-)-*N*-methylcoclaurines (4) to give *N*-methylcrotsparine and *N*-methylcrotsparinine respectively.

Tracer experiments showed that *N*-methylcrotsparine undergoes dienone-phenol rearrangement to give *N*-methylsparsiflorine. Double labeling experiment with (\pm) N [¹⁴C methyl, 1 ³H]coclaurine demonstrated that the hy-

Fig. 1. Alkaloids of *Croton sparsiflorus* Morong

drogen atom at the asymmetric center in the 1-benzylisoquinoline precursor is retained in the bioconversion.

Alkaloids of *Cocculus pendulus* (forsk) Diels

A programme aimed at screening Indian plants over a wide range of biological activities led to the observation of hypotensive and anticancer activities in the 50% ethanolic extract of the leaves and stems of *Cocculus pendulus* (forsk) Diels, a shrub which grows in the dry parts of North and Western India. Search of the active principles in the alkaloidal fraction in which these activities had been associated resulted in the isolation of five bisbenzylisoquinoline alkaloids. Of these cocsuln, cocsolin, cocsulinin (5) and pendulinin have been assigned structure and stereochemistry by a series of chemical transformations and spectral data⁴.

Cocsulinin (5), the anticancer agent of *Cocculus pendulus* could be biosynthesized by oxidative dimerisation

[†]In Commemoration of the 150th Birth Anniversary of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray.

Fig. 2. Alkaloids of *Cocculus laurifolius*.

of cocclaurine derivatives. Intermolecular oxidative coupling of two *N*-methylcocclaurine (5a) units could generate first the ether 'bridge' between the benzylic portions. The two ether linkages between the isoquinoline portions as present in 5 could then be formed by intramolecular oxidative coupling. 6-De-*O*-methylation of *O*-methylcocculinin (6) would finally give rise to 5. The feeding results strongly supported the following sequence for the biosynthesis of cocculinin (5) in *Cocculus laurifolius* DC 5 norcocclaurine → cocclaurine (+)-*S*-*N*-methylcocclaurine (5a) → dimerisation → (+)-(*S,S*)-*O*-methylcocculinin (6) → cocculinin (5).

Alkaloids of *Cocculus laurifolius* DC

A search for active principles in the alkaloidal fraction of the leaves of *C. laurifolius*, in which neuromuscular and hypotensive activities were concentrated led to the isolation of a hitherto unknown group of alkaloids now named abnormal *Erythrina* alkaloids such as isococculidine⁶, coccupine⁷, cocculitine⁸, coccolinine⁹, coccupinine¹⁰, and the dibenz[*d,f*]azonine alkaloids, laurifonine, laurifine and laurifinine¹¹. Thorough investigation of the alkaloidal constituents of the plant revealed that *C. laurifolius* is also a source of a large variety of 1-benzylisoquinoline derived alkaloids. This was the first plant species which produced both abnormal *Erythrina* and normal *Erythrina* alkaloids.

Of the various bases isolated from *C. laurifolius*¹² isococculidine, the major alkaloid of the leaves of the plant was found to have neuromuscular blocking and hypotensive activities. Cocculidine and cocculine exhibited hypotensive activity. This activity in these bases was due to ganglionic blocking action. The quaternary aporphine alkaloids magnoflorine and laurifoline chloride, *O*-methylisocorydine, isocordine, boldine methochlorides exhibited *d*-tubocurarine like curarising action on sciatic skeletal muscles. These quaternary bases induced hypotensive effects in dogs, cats and rabbits. This activity was found due to ganglionic blocking action of the bases on various sympathetic and *para* sympathetic ganglia.

Fig. 3. Biosynthesis of dibenz[*d,f*]azonine alkaloids (11-13).

Cocculidine (7) and cocculine (8), the hypotensive alkaloids of *Cocculus laurifolius* DC can be formed in nature from norprotosinomenine (9), an established precursor of *Erythrina* alkaloids. In the bioconversion one of the oxygen function of the precursor can be eliminated by dienonebenzene rearrangement. Feeding experiments strongly supported the following sequence for the bio-

synthesis of cocculidine (7) and cocculine (8) : tyrosine (\pm)-norlaudanoline \rightarrow (*S*)-*N*-norprotosinomenine \rightarrow cocculidine (7) \rightarrow cocculine (8)¹³.

Cocculus laurifolius DC was found as a source of a variety of 1-benzyltetrahydroisoquinoline derived alkaloids. Our interest in the alkaloids arose when hypotensive activity was observed in the 50% aqueous ethanolic extract of the leaves of the plant. A search for the active principles in the extract resulted in the isolation of three new dibenz[*d,f*]azonine bases, laurifine, laurifonine and laurifinine assigned the structures (11), (12) and (13) respectively¹⁴. The structure were established by chemical and spectroscopic studies.

The biogenesis of dibenz[*d,f*]azonine bases has been discussed. They can be derived in nature from 1-benzyltetrahydroisoquinoline precursors¹⁴. Norprotosinomenine (10) has been demonstrated by tracer experiments to yield *in vivo* 6,7,8,9-tetrahydro-2,12-dimethoxy-5*H*-dibenz[*d,f*]azonine-3,11-diol which in turn gives rise in nature to *Erythrina* alkaloids.

Cocsulin (15), a representative of the bisbenzylisoquinoline alkaloids having a dibenzo-*p*-dioxin system could be formed in nature by oxidative dimerization of coclaurine derivatives. Intermolecular oxidative coupling of two *N*-methylcoclaurine (4) units would lead to dauricine type intermediate which in turn can undergo intramolecular oxidative coupling to generate a dimer. Two possibilities could be considered for the formation of the dibenzo-*p*-dioxin system as is present in (15). In one the intermediate is oxidized to the corresponding phenoxy cation which is then substituted into ring A. Loss of CH_3O^+ can generate (6). A similar mechanism¹⁵ involving radical substitution has also been discussed.

Feeding experiments established that cocsulin (15) is specifically biosynthesized from *N*-methylcoclaurine (4). Parallel feedings with (+)-(*S*)- and (-)-(*R*)-*N*-methylcoclaurines showed that the stereospecificity is maintained in the oxidative dimerization of *N*-methylcoclaurine into cocsulin. The *S*-form was incorporated into cocculine about 60 times more efficiently than the *R*-form.

Biosynthesis of thalicarpine (19)

Tumor inhibitory base, thalicarpine (19) which also exhibited hypotensive activity, is a representative of

Fig. 4. Biosynthesis of thalicarpine (19).

aporphine-1-benzylisoquinoline alkaloids¹⁷. Biogenetically thalicarpine (19) is unique. It is one of the rare dimeric alkaloid which can derived in nature from two reticuline (16) units. Alternately it could also be formed by oxidative coupling of reticuline (16) with *N*-methylaurotetanine (17). Feeding experiments were conducted with the radiolabelled precursors. Biosynthetic thalicarpine (19) derived from (\pm) reticuline feedings was subjected to sodium liquid ammonia reductive fission to give (-)-6'-hydroxylaudanosine and (+)-2,10-dimethoxy aporphine. The former had essentially 2/3 molar activity and the latter 1/2 molar activity of the parent base in accordance with the theory. The foregoing experiments thus established that both the "halves" of thalicarpine are derived from reticuline in *Cocculus laurifolius*.

Alkaloids of *Stephania glabra*¹⁸

S. glabra (menispermaceae) a climber is indigenous to lower Himalayas. Extract of the rhizome of the plant has long been used by the natives for various ailments. Hypensive and spasmolytic activities were confirmed in the ethanolic extract of the plant when put to a broad biological screen. Reinvestigation of the alkaloidal constituents of the plant resulted in the isolation of two bisbenzyl isoquinoline, five tetrahydroprotoberberine, two proaporphine and four quaternary protoberberine alkaloids. Of the isolated bases tetrahydropalmatine hydrochloride caused hyperthermia in rats, palmatine was found to possess AcTH like bactericidal and anticholinesterase effect. Stepharine possessed antihypertensive properties. Cycleanine exhibited antitumour activity. Pronuciferine was found to have spasmolytic activity.

Alkaloids of *Litsea glutinosa* var. *glabraria* Hook¹⁹

Ethanolic extractive of *L. glutinosa* when put to a wide biological screen showed spasmolytic activity. Chemical investigation of the plant resulted in the isolation of boldine (**22**), a base with physiological activity and five other aporphines characterized as norboldine, laurotetanine, *N*-methylaurotetanine, actinodaphnine and *N*-methylactinodaphnine.

Biologically active aporphine alkaloid boldine (**22**) was isolated by us from *Litsea glutinosa* var. *glabraria*. Boldine (**22**) could be formed in nature from suitable 1-benzyltetrahydroisoquinoline precursors. Feeding with (\pm)-reticuline showed that it was an efficient precursor of boldine. Labelled boldine derived from (\pm)-reticuline feeding was brominated to afford 3-bromo and 3,8-dibromoboldine. The former possessed essentially all the radioactivity of the original base whereas the latter was virtually inactive. The experiments established that reticuline is a specific precursor of boldine. Tracer experiments strongly supported the following sequence for the biosynthesis of boldine (**22**) in *L. glutinosa*: (\pm)-reticuline (**20**) \rightarrow (+)-isoboldine (**21**) \rightarrow boldine (**22**)²⁰.

Alkaloids of *Stephania elegans*²¹

Chemical investigations of the stem, leaves and roots of *S. elegans* resulted in the isolation of 9 alkaloids characterized by physico-chemical data and chemical trans-

Fig. 5. Biosynthesis of thalicarpine (**19**) and boldine (**22**).

formation as epihernandolinol, *N*-methylcorydaline, hasubanonine, cyclanoline, magnoflorine, isochondrodendrine cycleanine and isotetrandrine (**24**).

Isotetrandrine (**24**) the bisbenzyl isoquinoline alkaloid which was reported to exhibit anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and hypothermic effects was selected for biosynthetic studies. Incorporation of radio labeled (\pm)-coclaurine, (\pm)-*N*-methylcoclaurine, (+)-(*S*)-*N*-methylcoclaurine and (-)-(*R*)-*N*-methylcoclaurine into isotetrandrine (**24**) in *Cocculum laurifolius* DC was studied and specific utilization of (+)-(*S*)- and (-)-(*R*)-*N*-methylcoclaurine demonstrated. Double labeling experiment with (\pm)-*N*-[¹⁴C]methyl [¹³H]coclaurine demonstrated that isotetrandrine (**24**) was biosynthesized stereospecifically from *N*-methylcoclaurine²².

Alkaloids of *Tiliacora racemosa* Colebra

The diastereoisomeric alkaloids tiliacorine (**26**) and tiliacorinine (**27**) representatives of the biphenylbisbenzylisoquinone alkaloids have been isolated from

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Fig. 6. Mechanism of formation of dioxan bridge in tiliacorine (26) and tiliacorinine (27).

Tiliacora racemosa colebr²³ and assigned the structure (26)²⁴. The absolute configuration at the asymmetric centers C-1 and C-1' in both bases could not be determined by the usual sodium-ammonia cleavage method²⁵.

Tracer experiments have demonstrated that the bisbenzylisoquinoline alkaloids cocculin and cocculinin are formed in nature by oxidative dimerization of coclaurine. Biphenylbisphenylisoquinoline bases of the tiliacorine and tiliacorinine type could similarly be formed in nature from coclaurine derivatives. Oxidative coupling of *N*-methylcoclaurine could give the biphenylbisbenzylisoquinoline intermediate. Intramolecular oxidative coupling could form the oxygen 'bridge' in the isoquinoline portion of the molecule. The methoxy group from the isoquinoline part of the molecule could be eliminated by the mechanism as shown in 25 as formaldehyde or its equivalent, to form the 1,4-dioxin bridge selective *O*-methylation can finally yield tiliacorine (26) and tiliacorinine (27)². (L)-[U¹⁴C]Tyrosine was initially fed to young *Tiliacora racemosa* plants and it was found that tiliacorine and tiliacorinine were being actively biosynthesized. Feeding of (±)-norcoclaurine, (±)-coclaurine, (±)-*N*-methylcoclaurine, (±)-*NOO*-trimethylcoclaurine and

26 : R1 = R2 = R3 = H
a : R1 = H - (S), R2 = H (S)
b : R1 = H - (S), R2 = H (S) 27 · R1 = R2 = H R3 = Me

Fig. 7. Biosynthesis of tiliacorine (26) and tiliacorinine (27)

dehydro-*N*-methylcoclaurine iodide demonstrated that these were being metabolized by young *T. racemosa* plants to form tiliacorine and tiliacorinine. As expected *NOO*-trimethylcoclaurine was not incorporated.

Labelled tiliacorine and tiliacorinine derived from (±)-*N*-methyl (3',5',8-3H₂) coclaurine feedings were separately converted into *O*-methyltiliacorine dimethiodide by treatment with methyl iodide-sodium methoxide. Alkaline permagnate oxidation of the dimethiodide followed by methylation of the acids so formed with diazomethane yielded in each case 2,2'-dimethoxy-3,4,7,8-tetrabismethoxycarbonyldibenzo-*p*-dioxan. Oxidation of labeled *O*-methyltiliacorine dimethiodine gave radio active (28) and radioactive (29) having respectively 2/3 and 1/3 radioactively of the parent base.

Parallel feeding experiments with radioactive (-)-(*R*)-*N*-methylcoclaurine and (+)-(*S*)-*N*-methylcoclaurine established (*S*)- and (*R*)-configuration at the asymmetric centers C-1 and C-1' in tiliacorine (26) and (*S,S*) configuration at both the C-1 and C-1' in tiliacorinine (27) in *Tiliacora racemosa*.

References

1. D. S. Bhakuni, S. Satish and M. M. Dhar, *Phytochemistry*, 1970, 9, 2573.

2. D. S. Bhakuni, S. Satish and M. M. Dhar, *Tetrahedron*, 1972, **28**, 4579.
3. D. S. Bhakuni and S. Jain, *Tetrahedron*, 1981, **37**, 3175.
4. D. S. Bhakuni and P. P. Joshi, *Tetrahedron*, 1975, **31**, 2575.
5. D. S. Bhakuni, S. Jain and A. N. Singh, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 380.
6. D. S. Bhakuni, H. Uprety and D. A. Widdowson, *Phytochemistry*, 1976, **15**, 739.
7. A. N. Singh, H. Pande and D. S. Bhakuni, *Experientia*, 1976, 468.
8. A. N. Singh, H. Pande and D. S. Bhakuni, *Lloydia*, 1977, 322.
9. H. Pande, N. K. Saxena and D. S. Bhakuni, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1976, **14**, 366.
10. A. N. Singh and D. S. Bhakuni, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1977, **15**, 388.
11. H. Pande and D. S. Bhakuni, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin*, 1976, 434.
12. D. S. Bhakuni and S. Jain, *Tetrahedron*, 1980, **36**, 3107.
13. D. S. Bhakuni and A. N. Singh, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin 1*, 1978, 618.
14. H. Pande and D. S. Bhakuni, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin 1*, 1976, 2197.
15. D. H. R. Barton and T. Cohen. *Festschr. A. Stoll*, 1957, 117.
16. D. S. Bhakuni, V. M. Labroo, A. N. Singh and R. S. Kapil, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin 1*, 1978, 121.
17. M. Shamma, "The Isoquinoline Alkaloids", Academic Press, New York, 1972, p. 232.
18. D. S. Bhakuni and S. Gupta, *J. Nat. Products*, 1982, **45**, 407.
19. S. Tewari, D. S. Bhakuni and M. M. Dhar, *Phytochemistry*, 1972, **11**, 1149.
20. D. S. Bhakuni, S. Tewari and R. S. Kapil, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin*, 1977, 706.
21. R. S. Singh, P. Kumar and D. S. Bhakuni, *J. Nat. Products*, 1981, **44**, 664.
22. D. S. Bhakuni, A. N. Singh and S. Jain, *Tetrahedron*, 1980, **36**, 2149.
23. B. Anjaneyulu, T. R. Govindachari, S. S. Sathe, N. Viswanathan, K. W. Gopinath and B. R. Pai, *Tetrahedron*, 1969, **25**, 3091.
24. M. Sharma, J. E. Foy, T. R. Govindachari and N. Viswanathan, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1976, 1293.
25. Y. Inubushi, K. Momura and M. Miyawaki, *J. Pharm. Soc. Jpn.*, 1963, **83**, 282.
26. D. S. Bhakuni and S. Jain, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin 1*, 1981, 2508.